

Design and development of electromagnetic control valve hydraulic coupler for scraper conveyor

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Abstract: Scraper conveyor is an important equipment for excavating and transporting materials in fully mechanized mining face. With the continuous development of computer technology and fluid mechanics, the research of hydraulic coupling has gone deep into all levels, not only limited to the structural characteristics of the hydraulic coupling itself, three-dimensional liquid electromagnetic calculation, three-dimensional design methods, but also involved in the optimization of the characteristic parameters of the hydraulic coupling. This topic is the technical design of the electromagnetic control valve of the hydraulic coupling, including the structural design of the main valve, the structural design of the pilot valve, and the three-dimensional modeling of the main valve. The research on the solenoid valve technology of hydraulic coupling conforms to the development concept and trend and has broad prospects.

Keywords: Scraper conveyor; Hydraulic coupling; 3D modeling

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Significance

China's thick coal seam reserves are extremely rich, accounting for about 44% of the total proven reserves. The underground mining of thick coal seam accounts for about 40% ~ 50% of the total national output. Therefore, the realization of safe, efficient, and high recovery mining of thick coal seams has an important impact on the development of China's coal industry. For thick coal m and extra thick coal m, if the method of one-time full height mining is adopted, the mining is difficult and the resource recovery rate is low; However, the layered mining technology has low production efficiency and high economic cost. Since the early 1980s, China began to test and study the comprehensive mechanized top coal caving mining. After several stages of introduction, promotion, improvement and improvement, high-yield and high-efficiency production has been basically realized by the end of the 1990s. Practice shows that, fully mechanized top coal caving mining technology is a kind of coal mining method with low investment, high output, good benefit, and safety guarantee, which is suitable for mining thick and extra thick coal seams with medium hard coal quality and easy to cave.

1.2 Hydraulic Coupling Technology

The hydraulic coupling structure adopted by the scraper conveyor transmits power through the change of kinetic energy generated by the medium on the impeller. The mechanical energy of the engine is converted into the kinetic energy of the medium through the pump barrel, and the turbine converts the kinetic energy of the medium into mechanical energy. Output to transfer momentum. Hydraulic coupling for scraper conveyor: first, vibration isolation. The coupling pump wheel is flexibly connected with the hydraulic turbine. When the motor output torque fluctuates periodically, it will not enter the working parts through the coupling, so the hydraulic coupling has good insulation effect; Second, overload protection. It can prevent the sudden increase of load torque or reduce the impact on the engine, to prevent transmission damage and other accidents; Third, long service life. The hydraulic coupling can operate safely without long-term maintenance except that the bearing has no wearing parts, to improve the investment efficiency.

2. Hydraulic Coupling

2.1 Working Principal

Hydraulic coupler is a universal component with high usability. This is a necessary component for the scraper conveyor to connect the motor and the machine tool. Its working mode is the same as the combination mode of centrifugal pump and hydraulic turbine. Although it is connected between the two shafts of the motor and the machine tool, it is obviously different from the coupling. It has the characteristics of overload protection, improved starting performance, stepless speed regulation, etc., which do not exist in various couplings.

Typical hydraulic couplers include pump wheels, spindles, turbines, housings, safety devices and other components arranged symmetrically. The casing and pump impeller can be fixed with links to prevent media leakage during operation. The input shaft and the output shaft are respectively connected to the motor and the working machine. Both the pump truck and turbine are impellers with radial plane straight wings. The spherical cavity composed of the pump truck and turbine wings is called the workspace, in which the medium is circulated, and the power is transmitted for work.

2.2 Influencing Factors

Working chamber shape: The shape of the working cavity of the hydraulic coupler is called cavity for short. It is a three-dimensional space limited by the groove surface between the blades. The performance of hydraulic coupling is mainly determined by cavity type.

Number of working impeller blades: Theoretically, when the blade is infinitely thin and infinite, the real situation of hydraulic coupling driving is the most obvious. However, in practical application, if there are too many blades, the effective volume of the impeller will be reduced, not only the area of the overcurrent surface will be reduced, but also the hydraulic loss will be increased, and the hydraulic circulation electromagnetic and its transmitted torque will also be reduced. If the number of leaves is small, the offset of liquid flow at the outlet becomes larger, the energy transformation during medium circulation is insufficient, the impact loss and volume loss increase, and the transmission torque decreases. The number of blades also has an impact on the overload coefficient. The hydraulic coupling with a relatively large number of blades has a low overload coefficient.

Blade inclination angle: Hydraulic couplers generally use radial straight blades with zero inclination angle.

Blade structure: The blade structure has a great influence on the characteristic parameters of the hydraulic coupling. For hydraulic loss, long and short blades are generally used to make the use area of the air inlet in the working impeller equal as much as possible; The second is to reduce the overload coefficient of the hydraulic coupling. The turbine blade structure adopts a large cavity, or the inner edge of the pump wheel and turbine is chamfered.

Other influencing factors: The viscosity, temperature, filling rate, resistance plate, auxiliary chamber, and volume distribution of auxiliary chamber of working fluid have great influence on the hydraulic coupler.

3. Design of Main Structure

3.1 Structural Design Main Valve

No matter how different the structure of each solenoid valve is, the control principle used as the basis is the same. After consulting the literature, the following mathematical relationship is obtained.

$$q_T = CX_R(p_1 - p_2)^\phi = CX_R\Delta p^\phi$$

Where, q_T is solenoid controlled by solenoid valve; CX_R is coefficient related to shape, liquid density, and liquid temperature; A_T is the flow cross-sectional area of the solenoid port, which is related to the shape of the valve port and the displacement of the valve core; ΔP pressure difference before and after the electromagnetic port; and ϕ is solenoid valve parameters determined by the shape of the solenoid port.

The form and characteristics of the electromagnetic hole greatly determine the performance of the electromagnetic control valve. As an important part of solenoid valve, some commonly used electromagnetic openings are as follows:

1. When the needle valve with electromagnetic caliber moves axially, the size of the annular channel is adjusted to change the electromagnetism.
2. When the needle valve with electromagnetic caliber moves axially, the size of the annular channel is adjusted to change the electromagnetism.
3. The axial triangle groove electromagnetic port has one or two inclined triangle grooves at the end of the valve core.
4. The slotted solenoid valve core is provided with an open slit; The liquid can flow into the valve core hole through the slit and flow out from the side hole.

3.2 Structure Design of Pilot Valve

If it is designed to close the ratio electromagnet and set the output to 0, the core of the main valve will be closed to avoid accidents. In order to achieve this, in this design, a demodulation spring is added under the speed regulating valve core to make the force of the demodulation spring large enough. When the proportional electromagnet stops, the pressure in the control room increases to the extent that the main valve stops. The pressure direction of the control chamber fluid to the pilot valve spool is exactly opposite to that of the proportional electromagnet. Therefore, at present, only the proportional electromagnet controls the status of the pilot valve spool, which is controlled by the proportional electromagnet and the return spring of the pilot valve.

4. 3D Modeling

4.1 Modeling Software

ANSYS is one of the most powerful finite element analysis software in the world. Compared with other software, ANSYS is better at nonlinear analysis. It can consider the analysis of complex problems, large-scale solution and multi system. The three-dimensional modeling of the main valve and the structural forming process of its key components are complex nonlinear forming processes completed by multiple components. In the whole three-dimensional modeling of the main valve and its key components and mechanisms, the optimization model is complex, and the optimization model needs to be modified in time during the modeling process to ensure the accuracy of the optimization model. ANSYS adopts the parametric modeling method, and many complex problems can be simulated through the combination of different modules, which provides a powerful tool for the actual parameter design.

4.2 Pretreatment Setup

The step wise guide to the setup is given below and for a better assumption Figure 1 to 3 is also included.

1. Enter the mechanical interface: double click [model] in the static analysis project to open the ANSYS mechanical interface.

2. Set the mechanical interface unit system: in the mechanical interface, click [units] on the menu bar to set the unit system to "metric (mm, kg, N, s, MV, MA)".
3. Define a named set: select the inner surface of any hole in the flange on the Y side of the valve body, right-click, select [create named selection], enter the name "fixed support" in the [selection name] dialog box, and select "apply geometry items of same" "size" "location Y" "OK". Select the named set "fixed support" just defined in the directory tree [outline], and you can see that 9 faces in the drawing are selected. The same procedure creates the named set "load" for the circular hole face at the other end of the valve body.
4. Define a named set: select the inner surface of any hole in the flange on the Y side of the valve body, right-click, select [create named selection], enter the name "fixed support" in the [selection name] dialog box, and select "apply geometry items of same" "size" "location Y" "OK". Select the named set "fixed support" just defined in the directory tree [outline], and you can see that 9 faces in the drawing are selected. The same procedure creates the named set "load" for the circular hole face at the other end of the valve body.
5. Define mesh for bolts and nuts: enter the entity selection mode, select the [mesh] branch in the [outline] directory tree, select any nut, and right-click -[insert]-[sizing] to define the cell size of 2mm. Select the newly created [body sizing], click object generator, define "graphical selection" = "nuts", "scope to" = "each entity" in the pop-up dialog box, and click [generate], which will automatically create a mesh division with a mesh size of 2mm for all nuts. The same procedure defines a grid size of 1mm for the bolt.

Figure 1: Defining name set

Figure 2: Define a named set for bolts and nuts

Figure 3: Define mesh for bolts and nuts

4.3 Static Solution

The static solution steps is described below along with Figure 4.

1. After setting the load and constraint, find the static analysis condition to be solved in the directory tree [outline], namely [static structural], right-click [solution], select [insert]-[deformation]-[total], and add the deformation result display; Right click [solution] again and select [insert]-[stress]-[von mises] to add the stress result display.
2. Right click [solution] in the [outlines] tree and select [solve] from the pop-up menu to solve.

Figure 4: Static structure

4.4 Viewing Analysis

After the calculation, click [total deformation] and [equivalent stress] in the [outline] directory tree to view the corresponding cloud map results. The detailed viewpoint is shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 5: Viewing analysis results 1

Figure 6: Viewing analysis result 2

5. End Notes

5.1 Conclusion

This paper has made a deep exploration in the field of mechanical design. The technical system design of hydraulic coupling electromagnetic control valve is used to convert the created three-dimensional physical model into file format. Based on understanding the function of the hydraulic coupler, the design scheme of the coupler electromagnetic control valve is given, and the three-dimensional drawing of the system is drawn. The electromagnetic control valve of hydraulic coupler consists of main valve and reed valve. Each function has an inlet valve and a discharge valve. The output rotation of the hydraulic coupling is adjusted by controlling the inflow of the inlet valve. The speed of the scraper conveyor can be slowed down by adjusting the solenoids of the inlet valve and the drain valve. The research of hydraulic coupling solenoid valve technology conforms to the development concept, conforms to the development trend, and has broad development prospects.

5.2 Advantages

The main advantages of hydraulic coupler applied to scraper conveyor are: first, isolation of vibration. The pump wheel and turbine of the coupling are flexibly connected. When the torque output by the motor fluctuates periodically, it will not be transmitted to the working parts through the coupling. Therefore, the hydraulic coupling has a good isolation effect; The second is overload protection. It can prevent the sudden increase or attenuation of load torque from impacting the motor and prevent the occurrence of accidents such as damage of transmission parts.

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